

THE MAIN PECULIARITIES OF LITERATURE DURING VICTORIAN PERIOD

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Abstract

The given article pays a great attention on the highlighted elements of Victorian period and literature. Rise of education and public literacy, development of novel genre, serialization of works in prose and poetry, improvement of children's literature, the existence of sensation and industrial novels, Social Realism, The New Woman Fiction were the most obvious features of the period. The appearance of The New Woman in novels caused women to understand their rights and they began to play an important role in the society. Male, as well as, female writers symbolized The New Woman in their works.

Key words: Victorian literature, periodicals, novel genre, prose, poetry, Social Realism, The New Woman.

Victorian literature involves period between 1837 and 1901 when the Queen Victoria reigned. In fact, the Victorian period is divided into three parts:

Early Victorian Period;

Mid Victorian Period;

Late Victorian Period;

Poets like Alfred Lord Tennyson, Robert Browning and his wife Elizabeth Browning and writers like sisters Bronte, George Eliot, Charles Dickens belonged to the early Victorian Period. R. Kipling, Th. Hardy, O. Wilde, R. Stevenson belonged to the late Victorian Period. Education developed and reached its peak in Victorian period. Until that when it was early Victorian period knowledge of public was low and inferior part of public like children and women were uneducated. Lower

class people did not have the rights to study so it caused to lose their rights in all spheres of life. Novel was the prominent form of literature. In early Victorian period long novels were written and published and writers began to write longer works like periodicals. It caused novel series to be emerged. Main reason of this was the rising of the social literacy. Another reason was that it was affordable to buy and read serial publications for lower class people. Writers were mostly from middle class that was because lower class people were mainly illiterate. British newspapers began to publish stories or articles which continued in the next editions. Mostly, works of Charles Dickens were given in the newspapers as the form of series. Dickens' characters had been emerged from middle class audience and their way of life related to the new middle class. So Dickens' characters became popular among the society no matter his works were criticized for their weak plots. His characters, plots were the samples of social realistic novel which was the main characteristic of the Victorian period. As the public knowledge was low, they had an instant concern about the God and Christianity. Drama also flourished in Early Victorian period. That was because main part of the audience was illiterate and they only could enjoy by watching plays. Oscar Wilde also wrote several works for drama and gained a career as an outstanding playwright. One of his famous plays was "Importance of being Earnest" in 1895. In Late Victorian Period, J.T. Grein established "Independent Theatre" and first works of G.B. Shaw staged there. In Mid-Victorian Period Charles Dickens wrote and published his critical works and attacked on some works of Early Victorian period. In the literary field Anthony Trollope appeared with

his realistic novels. Most characters of Victorian novel came from a lower class, struggled with difficulties and in the end gained fame and poverty. This kind of plot was a subgenre of Social Realism which was another main feature of Victorian Period. Most novels in this period were written in Social Realism. For instance, Charles Dickens' "Great Expectations" was a form of Social Realism. Pip, the main character, became rich unexpectedly after having encountered with struggles. He

described “real” with his all bad and good actions. Novel, as the dominant form of literature, developed and flourished. Features of Realism were seen in the framework of novels and it proceeded as the combination of Romantic Subjectivism and Augustan objectivism. George Eliot, Anthony Trollope, George Moore and George Gissing were prominent realists of the time. The last two influenced by Emile Zola and at the same time wrote against him. In Mid-Victorian Period Charles Darwin wrote his Origin of Species in the field of psychoanalysis. It became of Evolution of Human experience. In Late -Victorian period role of woman changed. They began to participate in social events and recognized their rights. This caused New Woman Fiction to be emerged in literature. Besides that, Education became compulsory for everybody. The field of printing developed and it caused to improvement and increase in quantity of newspapers, magazines and books. Novels continued to be published in a serial form. During 1860s, in Mid Victorian period a new form of novel, a new subgenre appeared. It was sensation novel. The best writer of sensation novel was Wilkie Collins. This form caused other subgenres to be existed: Gothic novels by William Morris and Oscar Wilde, utopian novels by William Morris and science fiction by George Herbert Wells.

Another essential significance of the Victorian era was industrial novels. Dickens’ “Hard times” was dedicated to millworkers. The main hero, Stephen Blackpool encounters with ostracism when he refused to join the millworkers’ union.

Highly characterized significance of the period was an increase in journalism and periodicals. British journalism and periodical writing flourished because of the cheap cost of printing.

Essayists wrote mostly about British history and criticized British society. Those were John Ruskin, Thomas Babington, Thomas Carlyle, Mathew Arnold. This trend – journalism- led to the development of female journalists like Harriet Martineau. One of the famous reformers like Florence Nightingale also wrote periodicals about important issues of the British society. Most important figures in

British literature contributed to the development of the periodical press. These figures were Charles Dickens and George Eliot.

Victorian period gave a birth to the development of the children's literature which was another main feature of the Late Victorian period. In this period, stories and novels included events about evil princes, princess and princesses, magical items and cruel queens. Lewis Carroll's "Alice's adventures in Wonderland" was written in 1865 and brought enormous success. Another story about Alice's adventure "Through the looking glass" came into existence in 1871. In Wonderland Alice experienced several rules of everyday life: The rule of language, the rule of social conduct and legal institutions. These works were often considered "the golden age" of the children's literature. No matter it was not written for children, "Robinson Crusoe" became the most popular work of the children's literature.

Beyond the development of novel form, poetry also flourished and became popular in Victorian period. Poets began to write long narrative poems as the writers wrote novel series. Such poems called epic poems in literature. One of the examples of narrative poems was "Aurora Leigh" by Elizabeth Browning which was an entire novel written in verse. This work made its author- Elizabeth Browning- be the most admired woman poet of the period. Her achievements made the term "poetess" become popular and trendy. Her works gave masculine power to the female gender. This trend passed one to another and poets like Alfred Lord Tennyson, R. Browning experimented dramatic monologues and narrative poems in this period. Elizabeth Browning's next work, "Songs before congress" which was dedicated to the American slavery was admitted by many admirers. It included nine poems. G.H. Lewes in his "Blackwood's" said "her place among the immortals is secure" when talking about E. Browning after her death. Chorley judged her "greatest poetess of any time" in his "Athenaeum". After that a new climate for women writers appeared. In 1858, Barbara Leigh Bodichon and Bessie Rayner Parkes founded the English Women's Journal and then after 2 years they established the Portfolio Society in

order women writers and artists to share their works in poetry and painting. Jean Ingelow was considered to be one of the best poets of mid-1860s. Her “Poems” was published in 20 editions and sold in 100,000 copies even in America. The most attractive woman writer who captured the public attention after E. Browning was Christina Rossetti. With her “Goblin market and other poems” she showed characteristics of her style which designed with colloquial word and rhythms. Interestingly, Rossetti’s poetry turned into much more religious meaning and the preparation to the life after death. In her later works life and death became common topics.

When we continue discussing features of Victorian literature, it is important to note the existence of sensation novels and The New Woman Fiction. The New Woman Question first appeared in 1892 by Mary Wollstonecraft and it influenced the mid- and Late- Victorian feminists. Harriet Martineau began Woman Question as the debate form and made upper class women get the education and a job in order to be an independent and get a role in society. Continuing this trend, number of feminists urged upper- class women to be active and get the rights of studying, working, voting and, even, divorcing. Such movements helped to make The Married Women’s Property Act in 1870 which let women control their own income after the marriage. As the result, from 1882 women began to control their property. First two women colleges were built in Oxford. “The New Woman” term was used by the writer Sarah Grand in 1894 and became popular in newspapers and magazines. The New Woman which had come from the prototype of Victorian woman became an icon for females of the decade. It was not the symbol of middle-class women, but ordinary lower class women and workers. At the end of the 19th century, The New Woman conception spread throughout the country and led to changes in the role of women, their rights and their position in all spheres of life such as: medicine, education, politics and law. Soon The New Woman became an object of popular press and fiction, even satirists made the representations of her as riding a bicycle and smoking a cigarette. This new phenomenon reflected a new womanhood of the 20th century. In the fiction The New

Woman came to the existence in 1880-1890 or in the late-Victorian period and referred not to the single genre, but multiple genres with a woman as a main character. The New Woman Fiction fought against a symbol of woman of male writers who always became an angel of the house. So the new form of novels in Victorian period was mostly based on the New Woman concept and represented dissatisfaction from the usual, ordinary image of women. And novels of this concept usually went against the idea that women's real space was home. The New Woman novels showed 3 areas where women felt oppression. They were marriage, labor market, suffrage. But some writers added love. A.R. Cunningham proposed two types of the New Woman novels: the purity school novels and the Sue Bridehead type of novels. Both types represented women as a victim of society and marriage. But main difference was that purity school novels did not deny marriage, but the New Woman fiction demonstrated traditional marriage as the degeneration of male in the society. The New Woman writers were mostly woman, but some male writers worked on this genre. They rebuilt the symbol of woman in the society. The new representation of woman of the New Woman genre was different from Thackeray's Amelia in *Vanity Fair* and Dickens's Esther Summerson in *The Bleak House*. Male New Woman writers were George Meredith , George Gissing, Grand Allen and Tomas Hardy.

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